

Serum Magnesium and Intra-Erythrocyte Magnesium Levels in Patients with Acute Myocardial Infarctus

Original Article

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In this study, we intended to commentate on whether serum-Magnesium (S-Mg') and intra-erythrocytic-Magnesium (Ie-Mg'*) levels are a risk factor for acute myocardial infarction in patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction (AMI).

Materials and Methods: The study included 57 (44 Male, 13 Female) patients with acute myocardial infarction and 35 control cases (23 Male, 12 Female) who did not have any coronary artery disease and did not use any medication affecting Magnesium (Mg) levels. Blood samples were taken from the patients included in the study and the individuals in the control group to measure S-Mg and Ie-Mg levels. In addition, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C), and total cholesterol (Total-C) levels of both the patient and control groups were measured. The patient and control groups were compared in terms of serum and intra-erythrocytic Mg levels. Besides, it was also examined whether there was a statistical correlation between the S-Mg' and Ie-Mg'' levels of the patient and control groups and age, gender, and smoking.

Results: While S-Mg* levels were found to be significantly lower in the patient group with acute myocardial infarction, no significant difference was found between the patient and control groups in terms of Ie-Mg levels. This shows us that Mg decreases in the extracellular space in the acute phase of infarction and may be a risk factor for coronary artery disease. Additionally, we did not find any relationship between age and smoking and S-Mg' and Ie-Mg'' levels in the patient group.

Conclusion: As a result, we can propound that serum magnesium level is low in patients with AMI. Therefore, we think that using Mg* therapy after infarction may benefit these patients due to the cardioprotective properties of Mg. Within the difficulties of measuring intra- erythrocytic-Magnesium levels and because of the cost-effectivity, also there is no statistical difference between patient and control groups, it would be enough measuring of serum Mg levels to evaluate this subject.

Keywords: Acute myocardial infarction, serum-Magnesium, intra-erythrocyte-Magnesium

Introduction

Acute myocardial infarction (AMI) is one of the diseases frequently observed in industrial countries. Approximately

1,500,000 myocardial infarctions are diagnosed each year in the United States. Myocardial infarction is responsible for 1/ Mortality in AMI reaching 9635 within the

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first hour following the infarction (1).4 of all deaths worldwide.

Coronary artery disease occurs for variable reasons and there are many risk factors predisposed to this situation. The main roles of these risk factors are; age, family history, smoking, hypertension (HT), hypercholesterolemia, low high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-C) level, and diabetes mellitus (DM) (2-6).

Magnesium (Mg) is an important element in the physiology of the cardiovascular system and in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, the relationship between CAD and Mg has been investigated for more than 30 years. There is a negative correlation between the ratio of Mg in drinking water and the frequency of coronary events, and it has been reported that high serum Mg levels help reduce coronary events (4, 5, 7).

The therapeutic efficacy of magnesium has been scrutinized in many cardiovascular diseases. These diseases are supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias (multifocal atrial tachycardia, polymorphic ventricular tachycardia, continuous ventricular tachycardia), AMI, congestive heart failure (CHF), and hypertension. Recently, there has been consensus that the lack of Mg amount in the diet is an important risk factor for HT, cardiac arrhythmia, CAD, atherosclerosis, and sudden cardiac death. Deficiency in serum Mg amount; is often associated with arrhythmia, coronary vasospasm, ischemic heart disease, high blood pressure, and sudden cardiac death. In cardiology, it has been proven that Mg contributes to the prevention of heart rhythm changes and AMI, protection, and treatment during open heart surgery. The point that all the authors agree on is that magnesium has an important role in both the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases (8-10).

In this study, we investigated whether these levels are a risk factor for CAD by measuring serum and intraerythrocytic Mg levels in the acute phase after infarction in patients with AMI.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out between October 2000 and September 2001 at Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Medicine, Research and Application Hospital, Department of Emergency Service. A total of 57 patients, 44 men and 13 women, aged between 38-86 (mean age 58.7311.52 years) diagnosed with AMI in the emergency department were included in the study, while the control group consisted of a total of 35 individuals, 23 men and 14 women, aged between 30-77 years (mean age 57.8241.66).

In the study, patients who applied to the emergency department with chest pain and were diagnosed with AMI with a pain onset time of less than 6 hours were examined. As a control group, individuals who applied to the emergency department solely did not have any disease history or drug use affected magnesium levels and could not detect a coronary event as a result of the examinations and tests were included. In addition, the control group and the patient group were matched for age and gender. Individuals in the patient and control groups were divided into 2 groups; smokers and non-smokers. Non-smokers for the last 5 years were included in the non-smokers group.

Diagnoses of Acute Myocardial Infarction:

Detailed anamnesis was taken from the patients who presented to the emergency department with chest pain. Blood samples were taken for routine biochemical and cardiac investigations. Electrocardiographic imaging was

performed with the Nihon Kohden EKG device. Patients with typical chest pain, cardiac enzyme (CK, CK-MB, Troponin-T) elevation, and typical ST elevation in ECG (1 mm for extremity leads, 2 mm for chest leads in at least two leads of the localization indicating infarction) are considered as AMI.

Measuring Magnesium and Cholesterol Levels:

Serum Mg levels were determined with the IL Test Magnesium kit on the ILab 900/1800 device, using the Bichromatic analysis method. Serum cholesterol levels were determined with IL Test MHDL Cholesterol, IL Test Cholesterol and IL Test LDL Cholesterol kits and TILab 900/1800 device using the Bichromatic analysis method. Intraerythrocytic Mg levels were determined with the Perkin Elmer AANALYST 100 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer system.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from our study were evaluated by using SPSS (Ver 7.5) computer program, the Man-Whitney U test, correlation analysis, and the Chi-square test. The approval of the Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Medicine Ethics Committee was obtained for this study.

Results

The mean age of the individuals in the control group included in the study was 57.82 ± 16.6 , and the mean age of the individuals in the patient group was 58.73 ± 15.2 . There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of age ($p > 0.05$). Of the 35 individuals in the control group, 23 (65.7%) were male and 12 (34.3%) were female, 44 (77.2%) of the 57 individuals in the patient group were male and 13 (22.8%) were female. There was no significant difference between the control

and patient groups in terms of gender ($p > 0.05$), (Table 1).

Table 1: General Table Comparing All Characteristics of Individuals in the Control and Patient Groups

	AMI	CONTROL
n(%)	57(%62)	35(%38)
Gender (M/F)	44/13	23/12
Age	$58.73 \pm 15,2$	$57.82 \pm 16,6$
S-Mg ^{mm}	$2,09 \pm 0,03^*$	$2,51 \pm 0,14$
Ie-Mg ^{tt}	$4,49 \pm 0,07$	$4,28 \pm 0,13$
Total C	$191,43 \pm 6,73^*$	$165,22 \pm 7,47$
HDL-C	$37,21 \pm 1,22$	$39,77 \pm 2,45$
LDL-C	$125,07 \pm 5,70^*$	$95,48 \pm 6,77$
VLDL-C	$29,75 \pm 3,87$	$28,85 \pm 2,65$
Smoker/Non-Smoker	44/13	23/12

* $P < 0.05$ & control

S-Mg^{mm}: Serum magnesium

Ie-Mg^{tt}: Intraerythrocytic magnesium

Total C: Total cholesterol

HDL-C: High-density lipoprotein cholesterol

LDL-C: Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol

VLDL-C: Very Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol

When the S-Mg^{mm} and Ie-Mg^{tt} values of the individuals in the control and patient groups were compared, no difference was found between the Ie-Mg^{tt} values ($p > 0.05$), while the difference between the S-Mg^{mm} values was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), (Table 2).

When the S-Mg^{mm} and Ie-Mg^{tt} values of the individuals in the patient and control groups were compared in terms of smokers and non-smokers, it was observed that the difference was not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2: S-Mg^m and Ie-Mg^m Levels in the Control and the Patient Groups

Groups	S-Mg ^m (mg/dL)	Ie-Mg ^m /mg/dL)
Control	2,51±0,14	4,28±0,13
AMI	2,09±0,03	4,49±0,07
	T=0,16 p<0,05	T=1, 42 p<0,05

Discussions

Coronary artery diseases and their major clinical syndromes, AMI, angina pectoris, and sudden cardiac death, are the major causes of morbidity and mortality. In the last 30 years, many risk factors related to coronary artery diseases have been defined and exposed. Age, hypercholesterolemia, family history, HT, DM, smoking, and low HDL-C level are at the top of the list (2-6).

Recent studies have shown an inverse correlation between water hardness and cardiovascular mortality (4, 6, 7). In the current studies, a new relation has been found that rareearth elements in our body may have a possible role in the pathogenesis of CAD. Some researchers have shown that Mg, one of these trace elements, has cardioprotective effects (4,6, 11).

It is not surprising that Mg deficiency is associated with arrhythmia, coronary artery spasms, and ischemic heart disease. While a decrease in serum-Mg and intraerythrocytic Mg concentrations has been shown in some studies in patients with AMI, there are also studies pointing out that serum-Mg values were normal (11).

The internal elastic membrane plays an important role in maintaining the elasticity of the coronary arteries. Mg is an element that is needed as a cofactor for the formation of this membrane in the body. The elasticity of the coronary arteries is more important than the other arteries for proper nutrition of

the heart. This elasticity allows the perfusion of the heart to be better. Since the elasticity of the coronary arteries will be impaired in magnesium deficiency, deterioration of coronary perfusion can be expected. Due to the endothelial protective properties of magnesium, endothelial integrity is impaired in hypomagnesemia. In atherosclerosis, after the endothelial damage caused by Mg deficiency, Ca²⁺ deposits tend to accumulate in the areas where the collagen structure is present. Therefore, atheroma plaques become calcified (11, 12). Atherosclerosis is negatively affected by the LDL-C/HDL-C ratio, and this ratio is thought to be provoked by hypomagnesemia. Dietary Mg supplementation does not cause a direct decrease in cholesterol levels, but it plays an important role in maintaining the elasticity of the vascular structure and increasing the amount of HDL-C. This reduces the LDL-C/HDL-C ratio and reduces the risk of a possible infarction. In addition, Mg prevents the accumulation of Ca in the micro-injury areas formed on the arterial wall (12). In light of the results obtained from many studies on laboratory animals, it has been shown that there is an interaction between Mg²⁺ and lipid metabolism. In short-term severe Mg²⁺ deficiency, there were differences in Total-C levels at different levels, while significant increases in Total-C levels were recorded in long-term Mg²⁺ deficiency. Besides, Mg²⁺ deficiency affects the fatty acid composition of plasma lipids. In Mg²⁺ deficiency, there is an increase in catecholamine release, so it is a potential situation that Mg²⁺ deficiency increases stress. Increased catecholamine secretion increases lipolysis. As a result of increased lipolysis, free fatty acid levels increase and these free fatty acids are saponified with Mg, thereby reducing serum-Mg levels (11-14).

Since we found S-Mg levels to be significantly lower in the patient group with AMI, our study also supports these findings.

Additionally, we determined the Total-C and LDL-C levels were significantly higher in the AMI group. However, the point that needs to be clarified is that it is not known whether the S-Mg²⁺ levels of patients who had AMI decreased during the infarction or whether the hypomagnesemia that was already present before the infarction deepened further. Because both hypomagnesemia itself causes an increase in catecholamines, and there is an increase in catecholamines due to stress during infarction. (13-14), This situation can only be explained by screening the pre-infarction S-Mg levels of patients with infarction. But this seems practically impossible.

Due to the cessation of aerobic metabolism during ischemia, intracellular ATP begins to be consumed. Since most of the intracellular ATP is in the form of Mg²⁺ salt, it has been reported that the amount of intracellular Mg decreases during infarction (14).

Hypomagnesemia in patients with acute myocardial infarction may be transient and serum-Mg²⁺ concentration may return to normal during hospitalization. Rasmussen et al. (15) found that the low serum-Mg and intraerythrocytic-Mg²⁺ levels in patients with AMI were lower at the beginning of the infarction compared to the later control levels. It is reported that serum Mg levels stepwise return to normal levels in an average of 12 days following the onset of infarction. This is probably due to the unilateral extracellular extravasation of Mg in hypoxic situations (15).

Artificial AMI was created by the coronary artery ligation method and it was observed that Mg migrated out of the ischemic area. During this ligation, the passage of Mg from the coronary sinus to the blood increased and the Mg content of the necrotic area decreased by 23-31% within the first hour after coronary artery ligation (15, 16).

Transient hypomagnesemia in patients with acute myocardial infarction may be due to the migration of Mg from the extracellular region to the intracellular space. At the same time, it has been suggested that this hypomagnesemia may be due to plasma expansion in the post-infarction period with a simple dilution effect (15).

Rasmussen et al. investigated serum-Mg²⁺ concentration and urinary and Mg²⁺ excretion amount in 13 patients with AMI. In the first 32 hours, they found lower serum-Mg²⁺ concentrations in the AMI group compared to the control group. They did not find the urinary Mg excretion amount to be significantly different compared to the control group (15).

Our study is in agreement with the study of Rasmussen et al.

Tsutsui et al. evaluated serum-Mg²⁺ and intraerythrocytic-Mg²⁺ levels in 49 patients with transmural AMI. They found both serum and intraerythrocytic-Mg levels to be low in the acute phase of infarction. Intraerythrocytic-Mg levels returned to normal in 28 days, while serum-Mg²⁺ levels returned to normal earlier (17). Bogdan et al. evaluated serum and intraerythrocytic-Mg levels in 72 patients with transmural AMI. They found low serum and intraerythrocytic-Mg²⁺ levels on the first and third days. On the 14th day, they reached completely normal values (18).

Pereira et al. evaluated serum and intraerythrocytic-Mg levels in 29 patients with AMI. They found serum-Mg and intraerythrocytic-Mg levels to be low at the beginning of the infarction (6).

The decreased serum-Mg²⁺ concentrations of these 3 studies (6, 17-20) show a correlation with our study. However, intraerythrocytic-Mg levels are inconsistent with our study.

As a result, in our study, while Ie-Mg levels in patients with AMI did not differ significantly compared to control cases, S-Mg levels were found to be significantly lower. Therefore, the measurement of S-Mg levels in patients with AMI will guide us further in terms of being both technically easy and cost-effective.

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